

Improvement of Seasonal Adjustment Mechanism for medium sized Scheffler Reflectors

Practical Training Report

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Abstract

Scheffler reflectors are fixed focus, polar-axis parabolic solar concentrators that can achieve significant concentration factors at relatively low cost. The technology is widespread in India, and gaining popularity for medium scale solar cooking and process steam generation.

Among other features the reflectors require a flexible structure to cope with the seasonal variation of the position of the sun. Deformation of the structure is accomplished by two telescopic bars fixed to the vertical ends of the reflector, which have to be adjusted manually every 3 to 5 days in order to get a good optical performance. It is reported that some operators do not do this often enough, because of the trouble of having to climb to the structure and adjusting the upper and lower telescopic supports in an iterative manner.

The goal of the internship was the design and construction of a mechanism to adjust the upper side of the mirror automatically upon adjustment of the lower telescopic bar. Several mechanisms were synthesized, and a simple device consisting of three bars and a mounting structure was selected, designed to detail and constructed. A fine tuning mechanism was included to cope with small variations in collector geometry and manufacturing errors. Preliminary tests over the installed and calibrated mechanism show a very good agreement ($\sim 1\text{mm}$ error) with the calculated required positions of the upper mirror. A year-round test is however required to verify if all the design assumptions hold under real operating conditions.

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1 Project Scope

The requirements of the project were stated at the beginning of the internship as follows:

1. Design of a mechanism to allow the quick and comfortable seasonal adjustment of standing, medium size Scheffler reflectors (8m^2 to 16m^2), with the following characteristics:
 - a. The mechanism should be as simple and economical as possible
 - b. It should be possible to retrofit the mechanism into existing systems
 - c. Optical performance of the modified reflectors must be equal or better than the original.
2. Construction and test of the mechanism onto an existing reflector
3. Evaluation of results and detection of other possible areas of improvement

2 Measuring of the test reflector

A considerable effort was necessary to achieve a coherent set of measurements for a sample 10m² vertical reflector. A detailed construction manual for 8m² systems is available, but measurements on a lying reflector of this size showed noticeable deviations from specification, especially on points C, D, E, and F (see figure 2) which so far had not been critical for the operation of the reflector.

Reflectors of bigger sizes (10m² and 16m²) are built based on the same manual and using overall scaling factors. In some pieces however, corrections to account for e.g. the increasing sizes of the steel profiles are not made. Distance h (see figure 2) was not scaled at all, and it is the same for 8m² and 10m² collectors. The determination of the actual method and the exact factors for scaling proved therefore difficult, and could only be inferred in a reversed manner, after all dimensions were measured empirically.

The measurement process was challenging due to the irregular geometry of the structure, and an overall lack of references (verticals, horizontals, and right angles). Different methods were combined, in an attempt to overcome this difficulty:

1. Direct measurement of distances between reference points, and calculation of point coordinates through trilateration (intersection of circles with known radius and known center points). A problem of the method is that small measurement errors propagate into large uncertainties, especially when the calculated intersection points are used as references for new points.
2. Measurement of rigs (structures of simpler geometry which are used as molds for the construction of the actual reflector). Problematic is that the rigs can bend or distort over time, and that free play during construction might account for additional deviations.
3. Measurement of relative distances over a picture of the reflector. If a photograph is taken from far away, with a good quality lens, distances measured over a plane perpendicular to the camera focal line should be proportional to the real distances between reference points in the picture. Drawbacks are that errors in the positioning of the camera induce perspective distortion, wide angle shots generate fish-eye distortion, and only relative dimensions can be measured.
4. Reconstruction of details from technical drawings of an 8m² reflector, using overall scale factors. Difficulties with unknown scale factors and methods have already been discussed.

Figure 1. CAD drawing of the rotating frame over a digital photograph of the test reflector.

Contrary to expectations, the third method proved to produce the better overall coherence in all dimensions, yielding deviations from direct measurements well within the construction tolerances of different reflectors. Several pictures were used to detail different parts of the reflector and to check for perspective and lens distortion; CAD software was used to draw on top of the pictures and acquire all necessary magnitudes (figure 1). Attempts were made to apply slight lens distortion and perspective corrections using image processing software, but the agreement with direct measurements only worsened.

The relative dimensions thus obtained were cross correlated with absolute magnitudes acquired from the other three methods, until a coherent and reasonably precise set of dimensions was compiled.

3 Mathematical modeling of the reflector

Given the unfeasibility of a year-long measurement to determine the empirically optimum deformation of the mirror as a function of solar declination, the data had to be estimated through modeling of the reflector. Munir (2010) includes a mathematical description of the reflector which served as a starting point, but since this work is mainly oriented to the design of the mirror structure, further insight was necessary for the development of the seasonal adjustment mechanism.

→ A simple model was developed, under the assumption that the deformation of the central curve of the mirror (xy -plane) to the theoretical parabola will yield the best fit for the complete dish. Adjustment in the transverse direction ($y''z''$ -plane) was studied with the aid of the model, but not considered for the design of the mechanism.

Figure 2. Nomenclature and system coordinates used for the mathematical description of the reflectors.

Figure 2 depicts the key points that were used for the modeling of a vertical Scheffler reflector. For simplicity the device is sketched for zero latitude, at 12:00 solar time, but all relations should hold for a reflector at any latitude and any given time, under the understanding that all coordinates are properly rotated.

Three different systems of coordinates proved useful when defining the model. The main coordinate system (x-y) was set with origin on support point B, x-axis parallel to the earth's axis of rotation, and y-axis over the mirror's symmetry plane; a second set of axis (x'-y'), with origin at the focus (G) and y-axis parallel to the incident sunlight, is convenient to write the equation for the parabola; and finally a third coordinate system (x''-y''), also with origin on B but solidary to the reflector's central beam, is useful to allocate points over the mirror structure.

The convention used to refer to vectors between different points is the following:

$$\mathbf{r}_{AB} = \begin{pmatrix} x_B \\ y_B \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} x_A \\ y_A \end{pmatrix} = r_{AB} \angle \theta_{AB}$$

Where:

$$r_{AB} = \sqrt{(x_B - x_A)^2 + (y_B - y_A)^2}$$

$$\theta_{AB} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y_B - y_A}{x_B - x_A} \right)$$

To work with vectors in different coordinate systems the appropriate translation and rotation between different systems have to be considered. A linear transformation in 2D consisting of a translation by (t_x, t_y) followed by a rotation by an angle θ can be written in homogeneous coordinates as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & 0 \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -t_x \\ 0 & 1 & -t_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

For the coordinate systems used, the following relations are obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= (x - x_G) \cdot \cos \delta - (y - y_G) \cdot \sin \delta \\ y' &= (x - x_G) \cdot \sin \delta + (y - y_G) \cdot \cos \delta \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} x'' &= x \cdot \cos \vartheta - y \cdot \sin \vartheta \\ y'' &= x \cdot \sin \vartheta + y \cdot \cos \vartheta \end{aligned} \quad \left| \quad \vartheta = \vartheta_0 + \frac{\delta}{2} \right.$$

Where ϑ_0 is the angle of the central bar during equinox. Note that the assumption has been made that the central bar will be parallel to the mirror surface along the year, neglecting the deformation of the central part of the mirror. In other words, when the sun moves an angle δ , the central mirror surface has to rotate $\delta/2$ to keep reflecting the light towards the same spot, and it is assumed that the central bar will be rotated by this angle as well.

The equation of a parabola with focus at G and which goes through point M can be written as:

$$y' = \frac{x'^2}{4p} - p \quad \left| \quad p = \frac{1}{2}(r_{GM} - y_M')$$

Where, according to the conventions discussed above:

$$r_{GM} = \sqrt{(x_G - x_M)^2 + (y_G - y_M)^2}$$

$$y_M' = (x_M - x_G) \cdot \sin \delta + (y_M - y_G) \cdot \cos \delta$$

The x' - y' coordinate system is used to describe the curve, so that the axis of the parabola is always parallel to the sunlight and that the focus lies at the origin of the coordinate system (G). Note that the focal length p changes as a function of δ even if the points G and M remain fixed. This can be easily understood by looking at figure 3. From this figure it is clear that not only the mirror structure must be able to rotate around the z-axis, but also some deformation of the mirror has to take place in order to accommodate the changing curvature of the parabolic surfaces for different solar declination angles.

Figure 3. Variation of focal length of the parabola for different times of the year. The focal length p is a function of the solar declination δ even if the focus G and a point M over the mirror surface remain unchanged.

3.1 Position of handles C and E

The mirror structure is a complex tridimensional body and its deformation under the influence of the forces applied by central supports and the upper and lower telescopic bars would only be accurately described using FEM analysis or experimental methods. However, considering that the required deformation is relatively small, an estimation of the position of handles E and G was made under the following assumptions:

1. There is no deformation at point V at the center of the main bar (see detail of figure 2).
2. Distances r_{Vc_p} and r_{VE_p} are constant, as well as distances d_c and d_e perpendicular to the mirror surface (see figure 4). Deformation at handles C and E is perpendicular to the lines going from points C_p and E_p towards the deformation center V of the mirror.

Figure 4. Detail of upper and lower handles for telescopic bars

The position of points C_p and E_p can be calculated as the intersection of the parabola and two circles, centered at V and with radii r_{Vc_p} and r_{VE_p} respectively. The problem can be stated as

$$y' = \frac{x'^2}{4p} - p \quad \text{and} \quad (x' - x_V')^2 + (y' - y_V')^2 = r_x^2$$

Where r_x is the corresponding radius (r_{Vc_p} or r_{VE_p}) for each handle. Substituting and rearranging terms,

$$\frac{1}{16p^2} \cdot x'^4 + \left(1 - \frac{p + y_V'}{2p}\right) \cdot x'^2 - (2 \cdot x_V') \cdot x' + x_V'^2 + (p + y_V')^2 - r^2 = 0$$

This equation has four roots, corresponding to the four possible crossings of a parabola and a circle. A Newton-Raphson method was used to find these roots, seed values of $x' = 1.8 \cdot x_M'$ for E_p and $x' = 0$ for C_p proved to yield the desired root at all declination angles. Once x_{C_p}' and x_{E_p}' are found, their corresponding y' values can be calculated from the parabola

equation, and then the coordinates converted to the main coordinate system by the relations already mentioned.

To find the actual handle positions C and E, translations of distances d_C and d_E perpendicular to the parabola have to be made (see figure 4). The slope of the mirror surface at any point over the center plane is given by

$$\frac{dy'}{dx'} = \frac{x'}{2p}$$

So the angle of a line perpendicular to the surface and solidary to the main coordinate system (rotated an angle δ) can be written as

$$\tan^{-1}\left(-\frac{2p}{x'}\right) - \delta$$

The required transformations for handle E (and analogously for C) are thus given by

$$x_E = x_{Ep} + d_E \cdot \cos\left(\tan^{-1}\left(-\frac{2p}{x_{Ep}'}\right) - \delta\right)$$

$$y_E = y_{Ep} + d_E \cdot \sin\left(\tan^{-1}\left(-\frac{2p}{x_{Ep}'}\right) - \delta\right)$$

Figure 5 shows the result of the preceding calculations. The deformation plotted on the right hand side is calculated as the difference between the actual required position of each handle (as calculated above) and the position it would assume if the mirror was simply rotated around point B. Only the component perpendicular to the mirror surface is taken into account.

Figure 5. Calculated deformation of handles C and E for different times of the year.

It is important to note both the magnitude and the direction of the required deformation. During winter, the upper and lower ends of the mirror have to be pushed inwards (towards the focus) some 40mm and 20mm respectively. During summer both ends must be stretched back

(away from the focus) 40mm and 30mm. These small deformations must be superimposed over the main rotation movement of the mirror which, as can be seen from the left hand side of Figure 5, supposes an approximately circular movement with arc lengths of 50cm to 100cm.

→ The main challenge that a seasonal adjustment mechanism must overcome is to achieve a precise deformation of the mirror (in the order of millimeters) while being unaffected by the main rotational movements of the mirror structure (tenths of centimeters).

3.2 Central support and $y''z''$ - curvature correction

So far only the behavior over the xy - plane has been considered, but the parabola is in reality a tridimensional revolving curve, and as the focal length changes, the curvature of the mirror must also be corrected on the transverse direction (parallel to the $y''z''$ - plane). Additionally, up to this point the relation between points B, M and V has not been established, and shall be discussed.

Figure 6. 3D Schematic representation of the central support mechanism. The $y''z''$ - plane (hatched) intersects the parabolic dish, yielding an elliptic curve of 'depth' e .

The equation for the parabolic dish in the 3-dimensional coordinate system $x'-y'-z'$ is analogous to that of the planar curve,

$$y' = \frac{(x'^2 + z'^2)}{4p} - p \quad \left| \quad p = \frac{1}{2}(r_{GM} - y_{M'})$$

We are interested in a cutting plane that passes through points A_1 and A_2 at an angle $\vartheta - \pi/2$ (parallel to $y''z''$ - plane, perpendicular to the center of the mirror surface). The equation for such a plane can be written as

$$y' = m \cdot x' + b \quad \left| \quad \begin{array}{l} m = \tan(\vartheta - \pi/2 - \delta) = -\cot(\vartheta - \delta) \\ b = y'_A - m \cdot x'_A \end{array} \right.$$

The resulting intersection curve can be investigated by substituting the equations above, yielding the projection of the intersection over the $x'z'$ -plane,

$$(x' - 2p \cdot m)^2 + z'^2 = 4p^2 \cdot (1 + m^2 + b/p)$$

This is nothing but a circle of radius $a = 2p \cdot \sqrt{1 + m^2 + b/p}$, but since the actual intersection curve lies over the inclined plane $y' = m \cdot x' + b$, it is easy to see that the curve is really an ellipse with minor radius a and mayor radius $a / \cos(\vartheta - \pi/2 - \delta)$. The small segment of the elliptic curve that actually lies over the mirror can be approximated closely by a circle with the same curvature radius as that of the center of the ellipse. It is a matter of standard calculus to prove that the final curvature radius will be given by

$$\begin{aligned} r &= 2p \cdot \cos(\vartheta - \pi/2 - \delta) \cdot \sqrt{1 + m^2 + b/p} \\ r &= 2p \cdot \sin(\vartheta - \delta) \cdot \sqrt{1 + \cot^2(\vartheta - \delta) + y'_A/p + \cot(\vartheta - \delta) \cdot x'_A/p} \\ r &= \sqrt{4p^2 + 4p \cdot \sin(\vartheta - \delta) \cdot [y'_A \cdot \sin(\vartheta - \delta) + x'_A \cdot \cos(\vartheta - \delta)]} \end{aligned}$$

The curvature radius r is clearly variable along the year, and ultimately a function of the solar declination. Figure 7 shows the result of the above calculations for the test reflector.

Figure 7. Curvature radius and focal distance as a function of solar declination angle.

The required depth of the mirror (distance e , see figure 6) can be estimated under the assumption that, when deformed, the mirror will assume a circular shape of changing radius but constant arc length s (refer to figure 8). In mathematical terms,

$$e_{req} = r (1 - \cos \beta) \quad \left| \quad \beta = \frac{s}{2r}, \quad s = 2 \cdot \beta_0 \cdot r_0, \quad \beta_0 = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{w}{2r_0} \right) \right.$$

$$e_{req} = r \left\{ 1 - \cos \left[\frac{r_0}{r} \cdot \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{w}{2r_0} \right) \right] \right\}$$

Where r_0 is the curvature radius for the resting mirror (at equinox position), and w is the separation between support points A_1 and A_2 , also at rest position.

Figure 8. Calculation of required mirror depth, from the curvature radius over the $y''z''$ - plane.

An adjustment mechanism is necessary to generate the required mirror curvature at all times of the year. The way in which the mirror structure is fixed to the rotating support is schematically represented in figure 6 and more in detail in figure 9, and is designed to approximately fulfill this role (the adjustment errors shall be calculated shortly). The weight of the mirror rests mainly on pivot points A_1 and A_2 , which allows rotation around the line A_1A_2 (parallel to Z axis). Point B in the rotating support runs along a slit attached to the center bar of the mirror, confining its movement to the x'' axis.

Figure 9. Correction mechanism for $y''z''$ - curvature. Distances h and k remain constant along the year, while the curvature depth e changes to adjust the curvature radius. Note that point B moves slightly inside the slit attached to the center bar.

For winter the mirror rotates downwards around A_1A_2 (pitch angle ϑ increases), the center bar is pushed forward and the depth of the dish (distance e) decreases. As the sun moves north towards summer the mirror must rotate upwards (decreasing pitch angle ϑ) and the center bar is then pulled back, increasing the depth of the mirror (distance e).

The *actual* depth of the mirror, as obtained from this support mechanism, can be modeled by looking at figure 9, and doing the following assumptions:

1. The side bars remain perpendicular to the center bar of the mirror, such that the distance k towards point M remains unchanged.
2. The lateral deformation of the side bars (see figure 8) is so small that their effective length (h) is practically constant.
3. The deformation of the center of the mirror is negligible, so that in that region its surface can be considered parallel to the center bar. Note from figure 9 that this assumption induces a small but noticeable systematic error, due to the curvature of the mirror.

There is a small offset between point B, which is fixed to the rotating structure, and point M, defined as the point over the mirror surface closest to the center of the slit, the second not only rotates around B, but can also move in the direction x'' parallel to the slit. Inspecting figure 9 it is clear that, if the assumptions hold,

$$x_M'' = r_{BA} - k / \cos (\theta_{MA} - \vartheta) \approx r_{BA} - k / \cos \left(\theta_{BA} - \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y_M''}{k} \right) - \vartheta \right)$$

$$e_{mech} = h - k \cdot \tan (\theta_{MA} - \vartheta) \approx h - k \cdot \tan \left(\theta_{BA} - \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y_M''}{k} \right) - \vartheta \right)$$

The last approximation is necessary to get two explicit functions in terms of the known constants r_{BA} , θ_{BA} , and y_M'' . It must be pointed out that, for the measured $10m^2$ reflector, points B and M are so close together that the first formula yields values within $\pm 3mm$, this movement is really negligible considering the significant free play which exists at the junction B due to construction tolerances. For the sake of completeness the small effect was nonetheless included in all calculations. The comparison between the required mirror depth and that obtained with the current mechanism is shown in figure 10.

It is obvious that there is a large difference between the required and the currently obtained curvatures of the mirror, especially during summer and winter solstices. This result, however, can be interpreted in two opposite ways:

1. The current support mechanism fails to produce accurately the required $x''y''$ - mirror curvature, and important optical performance improvements could be achieved in this area.
2. One or more of the assumptions considered for the model do not hold (the model is too simplistic). Namely, when the mirror surface is perfectly adjusted to the theoretical elliptic curve over the cutting plane $y''z''$, other parts of the mirror dish distort in an undesirable manner; and therefore the best possible 3D deformation of the mirror structure *requires* the error observed in figure 10.

Reality is likely to both possibilities to some extent, and only experimental investigations or a very detailed FEM analysis of the mirror structure could help to understand the situation and improve the optical performance of the reflector.

Figure 10. Calculated errors in seasonal deformation over 'y''z'' plane. Distance h in the test reflector was not properly scaled from the 8m² plans, the modified (corrected) response of the mechanism is also included for comparison.

3.3 Validation of the model

Due to the lack of measuring equipment, only qualitative observations could be performed to check on the validity of the model. Several experiments were carried out during the last week of February and along the month of March. Solar declination was calculated for the exact date of each experiment through standardized calculations [3], the required position of handles C and E for the given solar declination was obtained as described in section 3.1, and the required calculated length of the telescopic bars r_{CD} and r_{EF} was applied to the test reflector.

→ Very good focusing of the light (qualitatively equal to the best possible case) was observed in all experiments after setting the length of the bars to the calculated values. Quantitative measurements spread along a whole year are needed to decide whether this method of adjustment actually yields the best optical performance of the reflector.

4 Synthesis of alternative mechanisms

Once the position of handles C and E could be calculated with reasonable precision for any solar declination angle, several mechanisms were synthesized graphically to achieve an automatic positioning of the upper handle E as a function of the movement of the lower half of the mirror.

A simple mechanical transmission for manual adjustment of the upper handle (figure 11-left) was also considered but then discarded. The system would have been as complicated as any of the semi-automatic mechanisms, while not providing a real improvement of the ease of operation of the reflectors.

Figure 11. The first two alternatives considered for the mechanism. A fully manual transmission (left) would just avoid having to climb to the structure, while a semi-automatic version (right) was conceived to ‘amplify’ the movement of the center part of the mirror (the design had to be revised, see figure 12a).

For a semi-automatic mechanism the general problem can be stated as follows:

Given a position of point C appropriate to a solar declination angle, the mechanism must place point E at the appropriate location corresponding to the same declination angle. In other words, the mechanism must place point E as a function of the position of point C.

$$\mathbf{r}_C = \mathbf{f}_c(\delta) , \mathbf{r}_E = \mathbf{f}_e(\delta) \rightarrow \mathbf{r}_E = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{r}_C)$$

In design of mechanisms the problem is known as *function synthesis*. Except in very simple cases it is generally not possible to achieve an exact solution. What is usually done is to find a mechanism which satisfies the function in a small number of points, and then try to minimize the errors on the rest of the trajectory.

The number of points which can be used along the trajectory depends on the number of degrees of freedom of a given mechanism configuration (parameters which can change within the mechanism, e.g. length of the bars, angles, position of the hinges). The most common case is a four-bar mechanism with two fixed pivot points, for which the synthesis can be made for 3 positions.

When designing a mechanism for a complete trajectory it is important to choose points which are representative of the whole path. As a rule of thumb it is recommended to take the Chebyshev nodes over the full trajectory, for n points over the interval $[-1, 1]$ the nodes are given by:

$$x_i = \cos\left(\frac{2i-1}{2n} \cdot \pi\right), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

In the case of three points spread over the interval $\delta = [-23.5^\circ, 23.5^\circ]$ the recommended positions are those corresponding to solar declination angles $-20.3^\circ, 0^\circ,$ and 20.3° .

Mechanisms were synthesized graphically using CAD software. Figure 11 (right) gives an idea of the way in which this was accomplished:

1. The position of handles C and E was calculated for the three declination angles just listed. These points, along with possible pivot points are fixed in the design space.
2. A mechanism of the desired configuration is drawn for each position (the three mechanisms need not be identical at this point). Constraints are placed in all joints, and the mechanism is tied to the fixed points in (1).
3. Equal-length constraints are placed between corresponding bars of the three mechanisms, so that they actually represent three positions of the same mechanism.
4. Some of the constraints can be temporarily relaxed to play with e.g. different pivot points, different mechanism configurations, etc.

Figure 12. Alternative mechanisms synthesized for the semi-automatic seasonal adjustment. (b) would have to be mirrored just like (a) to achieve the required overall deformation.

5 Analysis of the three-bar mechanism

The mechanism depicted in figure 12c was chosen due to its relative simplicity and ease of construction, even though it does not provide the precision that could be achieved by a more complex mechanism (e.g. figure 12a). A more in depth analysis was carried on to determine the optimum geometry, the loads that the different elements would have to withstand, and the positioning errors to be expected from such a mechanism.

Figure 13. Nomenclature and vector laces used for the analysis of the final mechanism

Since the position of points C and E is known, point P can be easily found for any given length of bars r_1 and r_2 . Looking at triangle CEP it is easy to prove that

$$\theta_1 = \theta_{CE} + \arccos\left(\frac{r_1^2 + r_{CE}^2 - r_2^2}{2 \cdot r_1 r_{CE}}\right)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_i = \mathbf{C}_i + r_1 \angle \theta_1$$

If the position of point P is calculated for three positions of the mechanism, point S can be found such that the distance $r_{PS} = r_3$ is constant. It is easy to prove that for the set of three points P_1, P_2 and P_3 , this condition is satisfied when:

$$x_s = \frac{k_A \cdot k_D - k_B \cdot k_C}{k_A - k_C}, \quad y_s = \frac{k_B - k_D}{k_A - k_C}$$

$$k_A = \frac{y_{p2} - y_{p1}}{x_{p2} - x_{p1}}, \quad k_B = \frac{x_{p1} + x_{p2}}{2} + k_A \cdot \frac{y_{p1} + y_{p2}}{2}$$

$$k_C = \frac{y_{p3} - y_{p1}}{x_{p3} - x_{p1}}, \quad k_D = \frac{x_{p1} + x_{p3}}{2} + k_C \cdot \frac{y_{p1} + y_{p3}}{2}$$

$$r_3 = \sqrt{(x_s - x_p)^2 + (y_s - y_p)^2}, \quad \text{should be the same for any } P_i$$

5.1.1 Calculation of Loads and Geometry Optimization

The previous analysis shows that a solution for the mechanism (pivot point S and distance r_3) can be found for almost arbitrary values of the lengths r_1 and r_2 . Furthermore, it will be shown later (and it can be seen in figure 15b) that the overall precision of the mechanism is not significantly compromised within a whole range of values for r_1 and r_2 . There are, however, cost implications of these choices to be considered for the design of the mechanism, namely:

- Length of all bars (longer bars → higher costs)
- Forces within the mechanism
(shorter bars → bigger forces → stronger profiles → higher costs)

To investigate the forces during operation of the mechanism, a simple deformation test was carried out. Different forces measured with a spring scale were applied at point E, perpendicular to the mirror plane (direction y''), and the change of the distance r_{EF} was measured for each case (figure 14-left). Considering the angle between the line r_{EF} with the direction of forces, an elasticity constant of 0.459kg/mm was obtained. The test was carried out at summer position, but it is reasonable to expect that the measured behavior should hold for year-long operation.

Figure 14. Measured deformation force at E, and calculated forces for the mechanism at all positions (for $r_1=1.9m$, and $r_2=2.0m$)

Multiplying the measured elasticity constant by the required mirror deformation (Figure 5) yields the normal force $F_{E,N}$ to be applied at point E. Forces along the bars can then be geometrically calculated:

$$F_2 = \frac{-1}{\sin(\theta_2 - \theta_{CE})} \cdot F_{E,N} , \quad F_1 = \frac{\sin(\theta_3 - \theta_2)}{\sin(\theta_3 - \theta_1)} \cdot F_2 , \quad F_3 = \frac{\sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2)}{\sin(\theta_1 - \theta_3)} \cdot F_2$$

As the peak tensile and compressive forces are of the same order of magnitude (figure 14), the three long bars are expected to fail under compressive buckling. Under these circumstances, the maximum theoretical load that a slender bar can withstand is given by:

$$F_{crit} = \frac{\pi E_y I}{L^2} = \frac{\pi E_y \cdot r_g^2 \cdot A_S}{L^2}$$

Where E_y is the elasticity modulus of the material, r_g is the radius of gyration (depending on the section geometry), A_s is the cross sectional area, and L the bar length. The minimum mass of a bar with given material and radius of gyration is given by

$$m = \rho \cdot A_s \cdot L = \rho \cdot \frac{F_{crit} \cdot L^2}{\pi E_y r_g^2} \cdot L$$

$$m \propto F_{crit} \cdot L^3$$

It is assumed that costs of material will be approximately proportional to the weight of the structure, so the figure of merit for the optimization of the mechanism was defined as:

$$Cost\ Factor = \sum F_{crit,i} \cdot r_i^3$$

Figure 15 shows the result of the above calculations for a range of values of r_1 and r_2 . It becomes clear that any combination close to $r_1 = 1.9\text{m}$ and $r_2 = 2.1\text{m}$ should yield low material costs while providing acceptable accuracy (which will be proven in the following section). The final choice might depend on other factors, such as the position of the pivot point S and its support structure.

Figure 15. Mechanism optimization: figures of merit for material costs and overall precision for different mechanism geometries.

5.1.2 Handling with errors: fine tuning features

Even if all the dimensions of the Scheffler reflector and the new mechanism are precisely those of the model, the mechanism will only be exact for the three design points. It is therefore important to estimate the magnitude of the positioning errors that can be expected, and to come up with mechanisms to reduce them to tolerable values.

First of all, to check on the errors that can be expected solar declination angles outside the design points, the reverse calculation as in section **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** has to be performed. If now point S is set and length r_3 is given, point P can be calculated in a similar fashion as it was before:

$$\theta_1 = \theta_{CS} + \arccos\left(\frac{r_1^2 + r_{CS}^2 - r_3^2}{2 \cdot r_1 r_{CS}}\right)$$

$$\mathbf{P}(\delta) = \mathbf{C}(\delta) + r_1 \angle \theta_1$$

The vector lace $r_3 - r_2 - r_{BE} - r_{SB}$ can be modeled as a four-bar mechanism if it is assumed that the deformation of the mirror structure is mostly perpendicular to the line r_{BE} . The actual position of point E for a given position of point C is given by

$$\theta_{BE} = \theta_{SB} + \arccos\left(\frac{r_2^2 - r_{BE}^2 - r_{SE}^2}{2 \cdot r_{BE} r_{SE}}\right) - \operatorname{atan}\left[\frac{r_3 \cdot \sin(\theta_3 - \theta_{SB})}{r_{SB} - r_3 \cdot \cos(\theta_3 - \theta_{SB})}\right]$$

$$\mathbf{E}_{mech}(\delta) = \mathbf{B} + r_{BE} \angle \theta_{BE}$$

As the required position of point E is known for every declination angle, the positioning error can be found by comparing the two values

$$\varepsilon_E = [\mathbf{E}_{mech}(\delta) - \mathbf{E}(\delta)] \cdot \frac{\mathbf{d}_E}{|\mathbf{d}_E|}$$

$$\varepsilon_E = (x_{E,mech} - x_E)(x_E - x_{Ep}) + (y_{E,mech} - y_E)(y_E - y_{Ep})$$

Note that only the error in the direction of \mathbf{d}_E (see figure 4) is considered for the analysis, as deviations in the perpendicular direction are in any case much smaller. The error is a function of solar declination, as it is clear from figure 16, so the figure of merit for mechanism selection (plotted in figure 15) was the root mean square value of the error at all declination angles.

Figure 16. Positioning error at point E generated by the three bar mechanism, assuming all dimensions are exact and $r_1=1.900\text{m}$, $r_2 = 2.000\text{m}$.

To investigate the effects of construction errors and differences between individual reflectors, a sensitivity analysis of the error was carried out. For the chosen mechanism geometry ($r_1=1.9\text{m}$, $r_2=2.0\text{m}$) the required pivot point S and length r_3 were calculated and fixed. All the defining dimensions of the reflector were then slightly changed ($\pm 1\text{mm}$) and the effects of this change in the positioning error at E were observed (see figure 17).

Figure 17. Examples of sensitivity tests for error analysis, positioning errors of handle E as a function of solar declination, generated by a 1mm deviation in r_1 (top-left), r_3 (top-right), x_s (bottom-left) and y_s (bottom-right).

All deviations from the model dimensions produce the same sort of error response, composed of a systematic offset plus an approximately linear error term (increasing or decreasing proportionally with declination angle). Fine tuning features must cope with the two types of error as independently as possible, so that the user can adjust the mechanism to minimize one type of error without increasing the error of the other type.

Most of the dimensions that can induce positioning errors are already inbuilt in the reflector and cannot be regulated for the proper functioning of the seasonal adjustment mechanism. Remaining possibilities are the length of the bars r_1 to r_3 , the position of point S, and possibly the position of handles C and E over the mirror structure.

For practical reasons the position of point S and the length r_3 were chosen as the fine tuning parameters. As can be inferred from the notes on table 1, if the position of point S is changed over the line $y - y_s = (b_{y_s}/b_{x_s}) \cdot (x - x_s)$ then the seasonal error drift can be corrected

without affecting the yearly systematic offset. The latter can then be minimized by adjustment of length r_3 , this does have an effect on both error types, but its influence on seasonal drift is much smaller than its offset correction.

Variable	m	b
	<i>1/rad</i>	<i>mm/mm</i>
r_1	0.589	2.76
r_2	0.169	2.07
r_{VEp}	-0.233	-1.71
d_E	0.053	-1.19
r_{Vcp}	-0.583	-2.13
d_C	-0.237	-1.83
x_G	-0.032	0.14
y_G	0.083	0.10
y_M''	0.276	2.47
x_M''	-0.351	-0.42
x_A	0.143	0.01
y_A	-0.159	-0.01
y_D''	0.105	-0.29
r_3	-0.423	-2.22
x_s	-1.036	1.02
y_s	-1.026	-1.95
$x_s - (b_{xs}/b_{ys}) \cdot y_s$	-1.575	0.000
$r_{Vcp} - (m_{Vcp}/m_{dc}) \cdot d_C$	0.000	2.368

Table 1. Errors in the position of handle E after a +1mm change in several model parameters.

Deviations are modeled as a linear function of solar declination:

$$\varepsilon(\delta) - \varepsilon_0(\delta) = m \cdot \delta + b$$

Where $\varepsilon_0(\delta)$ is the error at the corresponding declination angle with no deviations in any dimension (structural errors of the positioning mechanism).

Note that linear combinations of two parameters can be used to isolate either the systematic error component b or the seasonal drift m

6 Design to detail and construction

Figure 18 shows the final mechanism design and detailed technical drawings and pictures are included as part of the appendix. Some special features to be noted include:

- The support elements for the pivot point S were designed to allow retrofitting into existing reflectors, and easy fine-tuning of the mechanism during installation. Adjustment of the pivot point is accomplished by slight rotation of a fourth support arm, whose angle is such that allows independent tuning of yearly offset and seasonal drift.
- Adjustment of length r_3 is accomplished via a threaded rod attached to one of the ends of the bar. To avoid the use of a double thread (i.e. jackscrew) the joint at point S must be loosened, the bar length corrected, and the joint assembled again. This process would only take place a couple of times during the first operating year of the mechanism.
- For ease of construction and installation, handles C and E had to be moved to the front of the mirror (new support plates were welded to the structure). Most of the values shown along this document correspond to the original handle positions, and might change slightly after the correction.

- Two support cables had to be attached to the sides of the mechanism to provide stability outside the plane. The steel cables have to be fixed with springs, to cope with a reasonable seasonal variation of length.
- Locally available materials (standard steel profiles, bolt sizes) and manufacturing tools and processes were taken into account at all stages during the final design.

The mechanism was constructed and installed within 4 days, but if materials and trained labor are available this could easily be done within two days. The cost of all materials used is estimated to be lower than 800Rs (12€) not including waste.

Fine-tuning of the mechanism was done very quickly because the mathematical model for this exact reflector was available, so the position of the mirror for all declination angles was known. In other cases, however, adjustments might have to be done gradually along the first year of operation. Preliminary measurements show that once properly tuned, the prototype corrects the upper part of the mirror within 2 mm of the expected position (r_{EF} distance).

Figure 18. Sketch of the final mechanism design, and picture of the operating prototype.

7 Conclusions

A mechanism was designed and constructed, which significantly eases the seasonal adjustment process of a 10m² test reflector. The optical performance of the reflector is qualitatively equal to that of a manually-adjusted model, but further testing (along a whole year) is needed to evaluate the design.

A simple but detailed mathematical model of the reflector was developed to aid in the design of the mechanism, even though the model was not extensively validated by experimental measurements, qualitative observations (and the fact that the mechanism designed using this model appears successful) provide support in favor of the model predictions.

Remaining tasks and further improvements could be directed in the following areas:

1. Field testing and year-long evaluation of the constructed prototype; construction and implementation of the mechanism in other 10m² reflectors; Improvement of constructive details, evaluation of ease of installation and calibration.
2. Study of user acceptance and economic/environmental justification.
3. Scaling and design to detail for other reflector sizes.
4. Evaluation of the current transverse (y"z") seasonal adjustment mechanism, and the overall 3D deformation of Scheffler reflectors for the improvement of year-long optical performance.

8 References

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9 Appendix

9.1 Note on the calculations

Most features of the mathematical model and calculations described along this document are included in an Excel file which might accompany the digital version of this report. Effort was put to use the same symbols and the exact same formulae as those discussed along this document, but as the spreadsheet file was not really developed hand-in-hand with the model, minor omissions and inconsistencies might be found.

For any questions or comments please refer to the authors e-mail address provided at the beginning of the document.

9.2 Pictures of the finished prototype

A short video explaining the prototype can be found at:

<<http://www.youtube.com/user/MrHansGiebenrath>>

Pivot point S, and adjustment mechanism for bar length r_3 .

Joint of the three bars r1, r2, and r3.

Adjustment mechanism for the position of the pivot point S.

890 with centered thread

2 pieces

Part type	Number	Material	Unit Length (mm)	Material	Total Length (cm)
a1	4	Angle 50x50x5	50	Angle 50x50x5	26.7
a2	2	Angle 50x50x5	23	Square Tube 25x25x1.6	447.7
b1	1	Square Tube 25x25x1.6	1825	Angle 25x25x3	255.5
b2	1	Square Tube 25x25x1.6	1925	Flat 25x5	79.4
b3	1	Square Tube 25x25x1.6	715	Threaded Rod 1/2"	43.2
c1	2	Angle 25x25x3	635	Rod Ø8	26.9
c2	2	Angle 25x25x3	635	Tube Ø50x3	3.9
d1	2	Flat 25x5	70	Flat 50x5	34.2
d2	2	Flat 25x5	70		
d3	7	Flat 25x5	25		
d4	3	Flat 25x5	45		
d5	3	Flat 25x5	50		
e1	1	Threaded Rod 1/2"	130		
e2	1	Threaded Rod 1/2"	293		
f1	2	Rod Ø8	130		
g1	1	Tube Ø50x3	33		
h1	2	Flat 50x5	87		
h2	1	Flat 50x5	50		
h3	2	Flat 50x5	50		